

Relativistic Interferometry Using Aqueous Waves

Aswan Korula
ORCID ID: 0000-0002-8937-5137

June 20, 2023

Abstract

The Michelson-Morley experiment and its resolution by the special theory of relativity form a foundational truth in modern physics. This article investigates the geometry and sequence of events within a Michelson-Morley interferometer and proposes an equivalent experiment using aqueous waves that can be performed in any everyday setting with little preparation and without the need for sophisticated equipment. The arguments presented are at a high school level and serve to introduce young minds to the difference in observational perspectives experienced by two observers separated in the velocity domain.

Keywords— Michelson-Morley, aqueous interferometry, special relativity

1 Introduction

The equivalence of optical and aqueous interferometry is well established in theory [1] and practice [2] [3] and leveraged in schools and universities all over the world to teach wave theory. Let us attempt to realise an aqueous equivalent of the paradigm shifting Michelson-Morley (MM) experiment. The method of investigation is as follows:

1. We begin with the geometry of two flat triangles that are relevant to the discussions at hand.
2. Then we present a thought experiment involving ideal sinusoidal waves that travel, reflect and interfere with each other within the confines of a circular boundary.
3. Next we establish that our thought experiment is equivalent to the MM experiment and from this we generalise the MM result in order to predict the outcome of our thought experiment.
4. Finally we realise our thought experiment in a circular ripple tank and leverage on the equivalence of aqueous and optical interferometry to arrive at a curious topic for discussion: Why are Lorentz contraction and time dilation absent in our aqueous experiment?

2 Euclidean Geometry

On a flat surface, we draw any angle θ at origin Q bounded by two equal length line segments $QB = QB' = h$. We join points B and B' to points A and C such that the line segment AC is perpendicular to QB and centred at Q . We will restrict our arguments to the domain $x < h$. Fig. 1 illustrates.

Figure 1: Triangles ABC and $AB'C$ rendered on a flat surface

From fig. 1, we establish the following geometric truths:

1. If $x > 0$, physical measurements will verify the theoretical statement $AB + BC \neq AB' + B'C$ is true for all $\theta \neq 0, \pi, 2\pi\dots$
2. Since h is constant, curve BB' will take the form of a circle as $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$.

3 A Thought Experiment

Imagine an ideal homogeneous flat surface S1 enclosed by an ideal rigid boundary of geometrically circular shape (radius = h) and capable of transporting a travelling wave of the form,

$$\frac{1}{c^2} \frac{\delta^2 y}{\delta t^2} = \frac{\delta^2 y}{\delta x^2} \quad (1)$$

where the terms are as follows:

1. x represents the displacement of the measurement point from the origin of the wave measured along surface S1,
2. c represents the velocity of the wave measured along surface S1,
3. y represents the instant displacement of the wave measured perpendicular to surface S1.
4. t represents the time elapsed since the instant that the wave was created.

From directly above, we may project fig. 1 onto S1 without distortion such that the boundary of S1 is defined by curve BB' , a circle of radius h about point Q . Now let us agree that surface S1 supports the geometry of fig. 1 over all $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$ and $0 \leq x < h$.

We choose any point A on S1 and disturb the equilibrium causing an isotropic sinusoidal wave (wavelength = λ) to emanate from that point. As this primary wave expands, its wavefront will interact with S1's boundary generating innumerable secondary waves as it does so. Each reflection event along curve BB' generates its own isotropic wave and from physical measurements of fig. 1, we find that if $x \neq 0$ the statement $AB + BC \neq AB'_1 + B'_1C \dots \neq AB'_i + B'_iC$ is true (See fig. 2 which is a generalisation of fig. 1 over all $0 \leq \theta \leq 2\pi$). Let us invoke the following assumptions to debate the nature of the interference pattern at point C :

1. The wave we generate originates from a single point and comprises exactly one complete cycle of a sinusoidal travelling wave

- 64 2. λ remains constant in accordance with the law of conservation of energy [4]
 65 3. Reflections are instantaneous and lossless

Figure 2: A single isotropic sinusoidal wave is emitted from point A and reflects from the circular boundary generating innumerable secondary wavefronts. With reference to sec. 6.1.1, it is easy to observe that (i) from the perspective of the moving observer (revealed by setting $x = 0$), the reflection events from B and B'_i occur at *approximately* the same instant in time and (ii) from the stationary observer's perspective (revealed by setting $x > 0$), the reflection events from B and B'_i are separated in time *approximately* as a function of x and $\sin \theta$. In relativistic optical interferometry, this effect is recognised as the relativity of simultaneity.

66 4 The Michelson-Morley Experiment

67 Now we turn to theoretical aspects of the MM experiment in order to establish it's equiv-
 68 alence with our thought experiment.

69 4.1 Frames of Reference

70 For the purpose of further discussion, we refer to fig. 1 and establish the following eu-
 71 clidean frames of reference:

- 72 1. A stationary reference frame I_0 centered at point Q .
- 73 2. A moving reference frame I_1 that translates from point A to point C with some
 74 constant velocity v relative to arbitrarily selected origin Q .

75 4.2 Geometry and Sequence of Events

76 Consider an MM interferometer [5] moving through space under inertial rules (see fig. 3).
 77 By fixing $\angle B'_1QB'_2 = \pi/2$, line segments QB'_1 and QB'_2 form the arms of the interferom-
 78 eter. The arms are free to rotate about point Q and consequently each arm subtends its
 79 own angle θ measured from a perpendicular to line segment AC . Reference frame I_1 is
 80 fixed to the interferometric source and moves with constant velocity v from point A to
 81 point C .

82
 83 The event cycle begins with the source at point A marking the simultaneous emission
 84 of a pair of photons (wavelength= λ). As the entire apparatus moves with some constant

85 ($AQ = QC$) velocity v relative to origin Q along line segment AC , the photons are emitted
 86 at point A , reflect from mirrors B_1 and B_2 to finally arrive simultaneously (in phase with
 87 each other) at point C .
 88

Figure 3: Geometry of the Michelson-Morley experiment depicting the general case $x \neq 0$. Equivalent to our thought experiment and identical to fig. 1, we find $AB_1' + B_1'C \neq AB_2' + B_2'C$ but yet we agree that the outcome is a null result at point C .

89 As is true in our thought experiment, it is straightforward to recognise that in one
 90 emission-reflection-result cycle of an MM interferometer and for all $0 \leq v < c$, the locus
 91 of all points in space where a reflection event can occur is a physical circle of radius h
 92 about origin Q . In terms of scope, our thought experiment is equivalent to one cycle of
 93 an MM interferometer having infinite arms (See fig. 2). It is also a well established fact
 94 of modern science [6] that the MM experiment presents a null result for all $0 \leq v < c$,
 95 where c represents the velocity of light.

96 4.3 Conflict Resolution

97 The geometry of the MM experiment and its sequence of events present a paradox of
 98 unequal path lengths but only from the perspective of a stationary observer (reference
 99 frame I_0) i.e. in all experimental cases where $v \neq 0$. This conflict is traditionally resolved
 100 by the application of special relativity (SR). In order to reconcile the paradox of unequal
 101 path lengths, SR predicts the existence of measurable distortions in the structure of space
 102 and time known as lorentz contraction and time dilation. The magnitude of these effects
 103 is proportional to the lorentz factor [7] given by,

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} \quad (2)$$

104 Equation 2 predicts that in cases where $v \approx c$, lorentz contraction and time dilation
 105 grow to infinite magnitudes. For the purpose of further discussion, let us stipulate that
 106 the predictions of SR are true [8] [9].

107 5 Predicted Outcome in our Thought Experiment

108 We now generalise the results of the MM experiment to predict the outcome of our thought
 109 experiment (sec. 3). We reason this outcome as follows:

- 110 1. Both experiments occur within equivalent spatial geometries i.e. Points A and C
 111 are always diametrically opposite each other and always contained within a circle of
 112 radius h about point Q .
- 113 2. In both experiments, eq. 1 equivalently governs the properties of the waves under
 114 investigation.
- 115 3. Therefore if the emission event is identical in both experiments, the sequence and
 116 character of all other events within both experiments must be identical as well.

117 From this,

- 118 1. We expect identical results i.e. null results in both experiments.
- 119 2. Null results would create equivalent paradoxes in both experiments.
- 120 3. If SR can be applied in the optical domain, it may be also be equivalently applied
 121 to reconcile the paradox of unequal path lengths presented by our thought exper-
 122 iment. Noting that the terms v and c in the MM experiment are equivalent to x
 123 and h respectively in our thought experiment, we must predict imaginary equiva-
 124 lents of lorentz contraction and time dilation to manifest in our thought experiment
 125 according to the rule,

$$\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{x^2}{h^2}}} \quad (3)$$

126 6 Practical Implications

127 Let us now realise our thought experiment onto the surface of a circular container (arbi-
 128 trary radius = h) of fluid such as water. The experiment may be performed by gently
 129 allowing a single droplet of water to disturb the surface equilibrium, the location of the
 130 drop (point A) being randomly chosen (see fig. 4). The reader will soon see that practical
 131 concerns such as non-ideal waveform, circularity errors of the boundary, bottom inter-
 132 actions, meniscus, dispersion (non-constant wavelength), measurement errors etc. are
 133 irrelevant to the argument being presented. We refer to this experiment as the Water
 134 Wave (WW) experiment.

Figure 4: The Water Wave experiment may be performed using a circular platter and any suitable means to initiate an isotropic wave on the surface of the water. When viewed from directly above, this experiment is *approximately* equivalent to our thought experiment (see fig. 2) and by extension is therefore also *approximately* equivalent to a Michelson-Morley interferometer (with infinite arms) moving through space under inertial rules.

135 Conceding that the physical surface of the water and the boundary of the container are
 136 far from ideal, we invoke the *approximate* equivalence of optical and aqueous interferom-
 137 etry to assert that this physical arrangement at least to some small degree *approximates*
 138 the ideal properties of our thought experiment and equivalently, the MM experiment.
 139 Therefore if we were to physically conduct this experiment in a circular ripple tank, it
 140 is reasonable to assume that the outcome should at the very least *approximate* the ideal
 141 outcomes we have obtained from our thought experiment and the MM experiment.

142
 143 Put another way, we expect the ideal theoretical predictions of the MM experiment
 144 and results of an equivalent aqueous experiment to agree with each other within some
 145 acceptable bounds due to practical limitations. Accordingly we predict for the WW
 146 experiment,

- 147 1. An *approximately* null result. This result is easily verified by **experiment**. Rather
 148 than chaos on the water surface, it is easy to observe a definite convergence of waves
 149 around point C . In optical interferometry, the extent of this disturbance (measured
 150 perpendicular to line segment AC) is referred to as the *fringe width*. It is easy to
 151 observe that for all $0 \leq x < h$, the centroid of the fringe always lies *approximately*
 152 on line segment AC showing an *approximately* nil fringe shift. This experimental
 153 result supports the assumption that ideal outcomes of the MM experiment are indeed
 154 manifested *approximately* in the WW experiment.
- 155 2. If nature is consistent [10] in her implementation of optical and aqueous waves,
 156 then *every* outcome of practical optical interferometry/ thought experiment must
 157 be manifested *approximately* equivalently in the conduct of an equivalent aqueous
 158 experiment.

159 6.1 Relativistic Effects in Aqueous Interferometry

160 Let us now investigate if the relativistic effects observed in optical interferometry are also
 161 manifested equivalently in the conduct of aqueous interferometry.

162 6.1.1 Relativity of Simultaneity

163 Consider the spatial and temporal perspectives of two observers separated in the velocity
 164 domain. Recall that in the MM experiment, the observational perspective of the moving
 165 reference frame (I_1) is revealed by setting $v = 0$ (equivalently $x = 0$ in the WW experi-
 166 ment) and that of the stationary reference frame (I_0) by setting $0 < v < c$ (equivalently
 167 $0 < x < h$ in the WW experiment). Recall also from fig. 1 or fig. 2 that if $\theta \neq 0$ then
 168 in both WW and MM experiments, points B and B'_i are separated in space from the
 169 perspective of both observers.

170
 171 In **conducting** the WW experiment we observe that (i) if $x = 0$ (the perspective
 172 of the moving observer) then all the reflection events from the circular boundary occur
 173 simultaneously and (ii) if $x > 0$ (the perspective of the stationary observer) then reflection
 174 events from any two points B'_i and B'_j occur simultaneously only if $\sin \theta_i = \sin \theta_j$ i.e.
 175 only if the line segment $B'_i B'_j$ is perpendicular to AC (see fig. 2). In cases where $x >$
 176 0 and $\sin \theta_i \neq \sin \theta_j$, these reflection events are separated in time as a function of x
 177 and $(\sin \theta_i - \sin \theta_j)$. In relativistic optical interferometry, this difference in observational
 178 perspectives is recognised as that of distant simultaneity [11].

179 6.1.2 Lorentz Contraction and Time Dilation

180 We have already stipulated that the predictions of SR namely lorentz contraction and time
 181 dilation are true when we conduct relativistic interferometry using optical waves. We now

182 invoke the impartiality of nature [10] to predict that *approximate* effects equivalent to
183 lorentz contraction and time dilation must also be physically manifested in accordance
184 with eq. 3 when we conduct relativistic interferometry using aqueous waves. Let us test
185 this prediction.

186
187 When we **conduct** the WW experiment, we find that independent of x^2/h^2 , the time
188 interval T taken from emission to result remains *approximately* a constant showing that an
189 aqueous equivalent of time dilation is absent. Further, independent of x^2/h^2 , the boundary
190 of the surface remains *approximately* a circle showing that an aqueous equivalent of lorentz
191 contraction is also demonstrably absent. By setting $x \approx h$, eq. 3 predicts infinitely large
192 magnitudes of lorentz contraction and time dilation, but instead we observe that not an
193 iota of these effects are physically manifested.

194 7 Discussion

195 In general practice, we observe that nature has implemented the travel, reflective, refrac-
196 tive, diffractive, interference and superposition properties of aqueous waves *approximately*
197 equivalent to that of optical waves. Section 6.1.1 has demonstrated that nature has also
198 implemented the relativity of simultaneity in the WW experiment *approximately* equiva-
199 lent to ideal theoretical predictions.

200
201 At this stage curiosity should compel students to ask: Why do we not observe **even a**
202 **trace** of equivalents of lorentz contraction and time dilation when we conduct relativistic
203 interferometry using aqueous waves?

204 8 Conclusion

205 The paradigm shifting MM experiment is usually conducted at the university level and
206 necessitates the use of laboratory grade equipment such as lasers, mirrors and high pre-
207 cision measuring rods. The arguments presented herein combine elementary geometry,
208 thought experiment and the equivalence of optical and aqueous waves to present an *ap-*
209 *proximate* equivalent of the MM experiment that can be performed using nothing more
210 than a platter of water.

211
212 This approach brings the theory and practice of relativistic interferometry within the
213 grasp of high school physics students and may be applied in the classroom or any im-
214 promptu setting with minimal preparation and equipment.

215
216 More significantly, the argument presented demonstrates the power of invoking the
217 symmetry of nature [10] while investigating physical phenomena and re-inforces the simple
218 overarching dictum that the impartiality of nature reigns supreme in the *ordo cognoscendi*
219 of all physics.

220 9 Statements and Declarations

221 The author has no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this
222 article. There are no data associated with this article.

References

- 223
- 224 [1] J. Walker, D. Halliday, and R. Resnick. *Principles of Physics, 10 Ed., International*
225 *Student Version*, page 404. Wiley India Pvt Ltd, 2016.
- 226 [2] BBC. Required practical - measuring waves in a ripple tank. [https://www.bbc.co.](https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z97rsrd/revision/5)
227 [uk/bitesize/guides/z97rsrd/revision/5](https://www.bbc.co.uk/bitesize/guides/z97rsrd/revision/5). [Accessed 30-01-2023].
- 228 [3] Caltech Physics Demonstrations. Demo 20803: Ripple tank. [https://www.youtube.](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E0L0ExDtnds)
229 [com/watch?v=E0L0ExDtnds](https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=E0L0ExDtnds). [Accessed 30-01-2023].
- 230 [4] R.P. Feynman, R.B. Leighton, and M. Sands. *The Feynman Lectures on Physics,*
231 *Vol 1*, pages 3–2. Dorling Kindersley India Pvt Ltd, 2011.
- 232 [5] C.R. Burnett, J.G. Hirschberg, and J.E. Mack. Diffraction and interference. In
233 *Handbook of Physics*, pages 6–91. McGraw Hill Book Company Inc., 1958.
- 234 [6] Ch Eisele, A Yu Nevsky, and S Schiller. Laboratory test of the isotropy of light
235 propagation at the 10- 17 level. *Physical Review Letters*, 103(9):090401, 2009.
- 236 [7] Albert Einstein. On the electrodynamics of moving bodies. *Annalen der physik*,
237 17(10):891–921, 1905.
- 238 [8] J.C. Hafele and R.E. Keating. Around-the-world atomic clocks: Observed relativistic
239 time gains. *Science*, 177(4044):168–170, 1972.
- 240 [9] H.P Robertson. Postulate versus observation in the special theory of relativity. *Re-*
241 *views of modern Physics*, 21(3):378, 1949.
- 242 [10] R.P. Feynman, R.B. Leighton, and M. Sands. *The Feynman Lectures on Physics,*
243 *Vol 1*, pages 11–1. Dorling Kindersley India Pvt Ltd, 2011.
- 244 [11] Georg Joos. *Theoretical Physics*, page 230. Haffner Publishing Company Inc., 1934.